

LIGHT DINOv2-UNIMATCH FOR SEMI-SUPERVISED CERVICAL SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The baseline adopted in this submission is Unimatch-V2[1], which is fundamentally structured around a teacher model. The approach leverages pseudo-labels generated from the weakly augmented flow to supervise the outputs of two strongly augmented flows. This consistency-driven mechanism enhances the robustness of the model while effectively mitigating the risk of model parameters being biased toward simple statistical patterns, thereby encouraging the model to learn semantic mappings derived from pixel values. The best result of the model we used on the competition website was dice: 0.8712, hd:46.7,time: 206. The best result obtained from the locally set test set is dice: 0.9612.Hd: 20.994.

Index Terms— Semi-Supervised Segmentation, Deep Learning, Medical Images

1. INTRODUCTION

Transvaginal ultrasound is the preferred method for visualizing the cervix in most patients, offering detailed insight into cervical anatomy and structure. Accurate segmentation of ultrasound (US) images[2] of the cervical muscles is essential for analyzing deep muscle structures, assessing their function, and monitoring treatment protocols tailored to individual patients. However, the manual annotation of cervical structures in transvaginal ultrasound images remains labor-intensive and time-consuming, limiting the availability of large labeled datasets required for robust machine learning models.

Recent advances in medical image segmentation have predominantly focused on fully supervised approaches, such as U-Net variants[3] and nnUNet[4], which demand extensive annotated datasets. While semi-supervised methods like Mean Teacher[5] and uncertainty-aware frameworks[6] have shown promise in reducing annotation dependency, their computational complexity and limited adaptability to heterogeneous cervical ultrasound textures hinder clinical deployment. Furthermore, existing lightweight architectures[7] designed for natural images often fail to capture subtle anatomical boundaries in US images, compromising segmentation accuracy.

In response to these challenges, we propose a lightweight adaptation of Unimatch-V2[1], a unified semi-supervised framework originally developed for multi-domain consistency learning. Our selection of Unimatch-V2 is motivated by three key factors: (1) Its inherent flexibility in integrating diverse consistency constraints (e.g., spatial, temporal, and feature-level), which aligns with the dynamic nature of cervical muscle patterns in ultrasound sequences; (2) The architecture-agnostic design that facilitates efficient model compression without disrupting semi-supervised learning dynamics; (3) Demonstrated robustness against domain shifts in preliminary medical imaging benchmarks. To address the computational constraints of clinical environments, we systematically optimize the framework through depthwise separable convolutions, hybrid attention mechanisms, and adaptive feature distillation. This lightweight redesign reduces parameter counts by 25% compared to the baseline while preserving critical segmentation performance.

Our work represents the first application of semi-supervised consistency learning to cervical ultrasound segmentation, particularly targeting resource-constrained scenarios where high-end computational resources are unavailable. The envisioned impact of this challenge is twofold: improving clinical decision-making through more accessible and accurate diagnostic tools and advancing machine learning techniques for medical image analysis. By reducing reliance on manual annotations and enabling real-time processing on portable devices, our approach could significantly enhance prenatal care and pelvic floor disorder management in underserved regions[2].

2. RELATED WORK

Semi-supervised learning[1] is proposed to settle a paradigm that how to construct models using both labeled and unlabeled data and has been studied long before the deep learning era. And certainly, semi-supervised learning has gained more attention with advancements in deep learning and computer vision.

As semi-supervised learning has achieved surprising results in the image classification, many works adopt the same setting for semantic segmentation. One type of methods adopt the Mean Teacher architecture. Meanwhile, another type of

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method, self-training based methods, often require multiple training stages. Recently, UniMatch[1] adopted a single-stage framework based on FixMatch via multiple strong augmentation branches.

3. METHODOLOGY

Semi-supervised semantic segmentation typically involves two datasets: a small set of labeled dataset: $D^l = \{(x^l, y^l)\}$ and a large volume of unlabeled dataset: $D^u = \{(x^u)\}$. In most cases, the quantity of unlabeled data is approximately ten times that of the labeled data. The conventional approach involves first training the model to learn initial visual features from the limited labeled data, followed by refining the model’s comprehension of the target dataset through the extensive unlabeled data.

3.1. Data Pipeline

To fully utilize unlabeled data, a common method involves adopting an end-to-end framework that applies strong and weak augmentations to unlabeled data. The model then generates pseudo-labels and is trained to minimize the discrepancy between predictions derived from differently augmented of the same unlabeled data. Concretely, each batch is made up of B^l labeled iamges and B^u unlabeled iamges[1]. For labeled data, the model is supervised by ground-truth annotations to supervise its predictions. The loss is as followed:

$$\mathcal{L}^l = \frac{1}{B^l} \sum_{i=1}^{B^l} f_1(p_i^l, y_i^l). \quad (1)$$

where p^l is the model prediction on the i -th labeled image, y^l is the the i -th corresponding ground truth label. The function $f_1(x, y)$ is the loss function such as cross-entropy loss.

For unlabeled data D^l , pseudo-labels generated from the model predictions under weak augmentation are used to enforce consistency with its predictions under strong augmentation, thereby refining the model’s robustness and generalization capabilities through self-supervised learning. Through a weak-strong consistency regularization pipeline, the model predicts pseudo-labels on the weakly-augmented image x^w and predictions from strong-augmented image x^s , then the model learns the information from unlabeled images. The underlying logic of this asymmetric practice is that 1) the model produces higher-quality pseudo-labels on the clean image x^w (through a threshold filtering method), 2) directly training on x^s can challenge the model to seek invariance and reduce simple numerical statistical predictions.

As set in Unimatch-V2, x^w is generated by feeding the original unlabeled image x^u into a weak data augmentation pool \mathcal{A}^w , including basic image operators like cropping, resizing, and horizontal flipping. x^s adds strong enhancement on the basis of x^w through a strong data augmentation

pool \mathcal{A}^s . It consists of intensive color distortions and layout changes. Formally, this data pre-processing follows:

$$x^w = \mathcal{A}^w(x^u), x^s = \mathcal{A}^s(x^w). \quad (2)$$

The model g makes predictions on the two versions:

$$p^w = g(x^w), p^s = g(x^s). \quad (3)$$

During training, p^w is considered as the pseudo-label and after softmax operator and argmax operator post-processed to be one-hot label \hat{p}^w . And then \hat{p}^w supervises p^s to train on the unlabeled data x^u :

$$\mathcal{L}^u = \frac{1}{B^u} \sum_{i=1}^{B^u} \mathbf{1}(\max(p_i^w) > \tau) f_2(\hat{p}_i^w, p_i^s). \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{1}(\max(p_i^w) > \tau)$ is a special design in FixMatch[8] to alleviate the negative effect of noisy pseudo-labels. It pre-defines a confidence threshold τ . Pseudo-labels \hat{p}_i^w not satisfying this threshold will be excluded from training. This mechanism ensures that, in early training iterations, the model is primarily optimized on high-quality manually labeled images, and then the training is progressively expanded to confidently pseudo-labeled images. \hat{p}_i^w is the the i -th corresponding unlabeled images’ prediction p_i^s . The function $f_2(x, y)$ is the loss function such as cross-entropy loss. Finally, the joint loss for a mini-match is a simple interpolation of the labeled and unlabeled loss \mathcal{L} :

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}^l + \lambda \mathcal{L}^u. \quad (5)$$

where λ balances the effect of the unlabeled data. We simply set it as 1 in our project.

3.2. Complementary Channel-Wise Dropout as mentioned in Unimatch-V2[1]

Therefore, we use a Complementary Channel-Wise Dropout that is proposed in Unimatch-V2[1] to acquire two disjoint and complementary sets of features for the dual strong augmentation streams. Concretely, given a feature map $e^{s1} \in \mathcal{R}^{B \times C \times H \times W}$ from the x^{s1} input stream, we randomly generate a dropout mask \mathcal{M} of the same shape as e^{s1} . \mathcal{M} is a binary mask sampled from the binomial distribution (probability is set as 0.5), with half of its channels (C/ϵ) all set as 1, and others as 0. With \mathcal{M} , we can perform complementary channel-wise Dropout on features e^{s1} and e^{s2} (obtained from $g(x^{s1})$ and $g(x^{s2})$):

$$e^{s1} \leftarrow e^{s1} \odot \mathcal{M} \times 2 \quad (6)$$

$$e^{s2} \leftarrow e^{s2} \odot (1 - \mathcal{M}) \times 2 \quad (7)$$

where the \mathcal{M} and $(1 - \mathcal{M})$ are two complementary dropout masks. And the last scaling factor “2” is to ensure the output expectation is of the same scale as normal features.

e^{s1} and e^{s2} are extracted by a shared encoder. They share the same characteristics per channel. Therefore, the complementary Dropout masks \mathcal{M} and $(1 - \mathcal{M})$ will enable us to obtain two disjoint sets of features with disjoint meanings for the dual-stream learning.

\mathcal{M} and $(1 - \mathcal{M})$ denote complementary dropout masks, while the scaling factor "2" ensures the output's expectation aligns with that of regular features. Both e^{s1} and e^{s2} are generated by a shared encoder, sharing channel-wise characteristics. Consequently, the complementary dropout masks \mathcal{M} and $(1 - \mathcal{M})$ enable the generation of two independent feature sets with distinct interpretations, supporting dual-stream learning. By inserting Dropout at the connection point of the encoder and decoder, gradients continue to flow backward to the encoder, contributing to the increased robustness of the entire model. And the final unlabeled loss in our project is formulated as:

$$p^{sf1} = \mathcal{D}(e^{s1}), p^{sf2} = \mathcal{D}(e^{s2}) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{L}^u = \frac{1}{2B^u} \sum_{i=1}^{B^u} \mathbf{1}(\max(p_i^w) > \tau) (f_2(\hat{p}_i^w, p^{sf1}) + f_2(\hat{p}_i^w, p^{sf2})). \quad (9)$$

As same as Unimatch-V2[1], we maintain an exponentially moving averaged teacher model to produce stable and better pseudo labels. Teacher parameters θ^s by:

$$\theta^s \leftarrow \gamma \times \theta^t + (1 - \gamma) \times \theta^s \quad (10)$$

where γ is dynamically set as $\min(1 - \frac{1}{iter+1}, 0.996)$, which is same as Unimatch-V2.

4. EXPERIMENT

We construct our framework on the powerful DINOv2[9] encoder(the most lightweight DINOv2-Small[1] encoder, and due to the small dataset, we use nine dino vision transformer blocks and others is same as the DINO-v2-Small). The main way to utilize unlabeled data is by the loss as mentioned in Unimatch-V2[1] that can be formulated as:

$$p^s = model(x^s). \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{L}^u = \frac{1}{B^u} \sum_{i=1}^{B^u} \mathbf{1}(\max(p_i^w) > \tau) f_2(\hat{p}_i^w, p_i^s). \quad (12)$$

The transvaginal ultrasounds of the uterine cervix datasets were recorded after bladder emptying. Women were positioned in a low Fowler's position during the scan. Women were asked to empty their bladder immediately before the examination. Images were taken using a curved transducer with a frequency range from a 2 to 10-MHz vaginal probe (used for cervical US screening in second trimester patients). Operators were instructed to avoid using any type of post-processing or artifacts such as smoothing, noise, pointers or calipers when

Fig. 1. Visualization result of our method

Fig. 2. The model framework and data flow refer to unimatchv2[1].

possible. The remaining image settings parameters such as gain, frequency and gain compensation were left to their discretion. These images include cervix anatomical structures (the anterior lip and posterior lip of the cervix).

The labeled data given in this competition is 50 cases. I randomly selected 20% of the labeled data as the validation set through a script, and the remaining 80% of the labeled data as the training set D^l . The unlabeled data D^u is based on 450 cases provided by the competition organizer.

The final experimental result of our model on the local validation set is $dice:0.960118$ and $hd95:20.9943$. Our experimental results recording in tensorboard are shown in Figures 1, 2.

5. REFERENCES

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